

Ploughing timing shapes N₂O emissions from peatlands

Drained peat grasslands emit high nitrous oxide (N₂O), and soil disturbance during renewal makes them a major climate challenge.

Summer ploughing as an intervention

Grassland renewal through ploughing is essential for maintaining forage yield and quality, but the timing strongly influences soil processes and N₂O emissions. The traditional boreal practice, autumn ploughing (AP) followed by spring reseeded leaves soil bare over winter, a period with no plant nutrient uptake. In contrast, summer ploughing (SP) with immediate reseeded maintains continuous plant cover during the growing season, improving nutrient uptake and reducing microbial N₂O production. AP can also degrade soil structure, reduce nutrient availability, increase soil moisture, and remove vegetation cover, all of which enhance N₂O emissions. Therefore, performing tillage in summer is a more effective management option to lower N₂O emissions without altering land use. Main findings include (i) AP caused much higher and longer N₂O emissions, while SP produced only brief peaks that dropped quickly after grass reestablishment, (ii) SP significantly reduced total N₂O emissions over three years than AP, (iii) N₂O emissions per unit of yield were much lower under SP,

making it the more climate efficient option, (iv) Grass yields increased under both methods, showing SP's lower emissions didn't reduce productivity; faster regrowth after SP also cut nutrient and GHG losses.

Figure 1. Year 1 shows autumn-ploughed plots; Year 2 shows summer-ploughed plots and regrowth on the previous year's AP plots; Year 3 shows grass established on all plots.

Key message

Summer ploughing supports both productivity and climate goals by keeping soil covered with actively growing vegetation whenever conditions allow¹.

KEYWORDS

grassland renewal, ploughing, N₂O emission, cultivated peatlands, boreal climate

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¹ Semberg, S. *et al.* Timing of grass renewal regulates nitrous oxide emissions from a drained boreal peatland. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* **399**, 110155 (2026).